

ANALYSING EMOTIONAL DEPTH IN AI-GENERATED POETRY: A NEW FRONTIER IN COMPUTATIONAL CREATIVITY

Nazm Us Saqib

najmussaquib3@gmail.com

Mob. No. – 7881111304

Abstract–With the advent of Artificial Intelligence, many aspects of human life have been greatly influenced. Every field has some kind of AI aid to it, and literature is not vacuum to this influence. The new generative AI called ChatGPT has taken academia by storm. ChatGPT has been put to work in different situations in the academic world, from writing assignments to getting assistance on any specific topic to squeeze some creative writing out of it. This paper analyses several poems written by ChatGPT to investigate how the AI is dealing with different emotions like love, happiness, sadness, anger, and remorse. To carry out our research, we will closely examine a few poems written by ChatGPT. These poems were generated with the help of prompts that asked the AI to write poems about varying emotions. We want to find out how ChatGPT expresses emotions in its poems and how it deals with feelings.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Poetry, Emotions, Close reading, AI-generated literature.

In an age where the boundaries between science and science fiction blur with each passing day, the realm of artificial intelligence (AI) stands as a testament to human ingenuity and innovation. I find myself irresistibly drawn to the captivating narratives woven by the ever-evolving field of AI, particularly the enchanting tapestry of Generative AI. In this paper, we embark on a literary exploration that transcends the conventional confines of our discipline to delve deep into the fascinating world of AI, with a special focus on ChatGPT. It is an exciting advancement in Generative AI which is rapidly reshaping the boundaries of human creativity, language, and expression. The concept of artificial intelligence has lingered in the realm of human imagination for centuries. Its materialization, however, as a transformative force in our lives is a recent phenomenon that has left an indelible mark on the very fabric of our society. AI, in its broadest sense, refers to the development of computer systems capable of performing tasks that typically require human intelligence, such as problem-solving, learning, reasoning, and decision-making. It encompasses a wide spectrum of applications, from self-driving cars and medical diagnosis to natural language processing and facial recognition, making it a formidable presence in our daily existence. Yet,

the term “AI” is not a monolithic entity but rather an intricate mosaic of subfields, each with its unique characteristics and functions. At the heart of this mosaic lies Generative AI, a subset that has ignited the imagination of artists, linguists, and writers alike. Generative AI, in essence, involves the creation of algorithms and models that possess the remarkable ability to generate new, human-like content autonomously. This content can take various forms, including text, images, music, and even entire stories. This singular capacity to synthesize new creations has profound implications for the realms of literature, art, and culture, as it challenges the very essence of what it means to be creative and sentient. In this context, Generative AI emerges as a literary Prometheus, imparting the gift of creation to algorithms and machines. It challenges our preconceived notions of authorship, creativity, and storytelling, as it enables computers to craft prose, poetry, and narratives that are often indistinguishable from their human counterparts. This newfound ability raises fundamental questions about the nature of creativity, the role of the author, and the authenticity of artistic expression. Is creativity, after all, a product of human consciousness alone, or can it be algorithmically engineered? The question lies at the heart of the inquiry

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undertaken in this paper, as the aim of this research is to deal with poems that have been written through ChatGPT. To answer the question, this paper performs a close reading of the produced results and analyses if it was a success for GPT in truly capturing the essence of human emotions and feelings. How is AI able to write poems?- In an article published on BigThink, Michael Wooldridge explains how ChatGPT works and generates texts, he says that this is just a sort of auto-completion, the one that we use in our smartphone's keyboard. Wooldridge writes that in being able to produce text so efficiently, ChatGPT uses what are called Large Language Models (LLMs). The LLM that is also known as GPT has the entire internet as its training data. The GPT has 575 GB of training data text, which is a huge number. Thus, GPT has learned of every way that was ever uploaded on the internet of writing text, and thus it writes in the same manner. But Wooldridge writes what GPT lacks is perception, the language model can imitate a Shakespearean sonnet because it has read all the 154 sonnets on the internet, but can it write it in a new way, no it can't. That brings up the question: is ChatGPT a true AI? Which Wooldridge denies, he writes that yes it is a part of AI which is called symbolic AI, but it is far from what is known as true AI which has some

similarities to the human mind. An article, published on the website of Spanish newspaper El País, talks about the capabilities of AI language models in generating poems. The article elucidates on why art pieces written by AIs can never be claimed as intellectual property. "Perhaps a machine can create art... but it won't be protected by intellectual property law, because for this to occur, there must be an author. As such – except in rare cases – only [human beings] can be authors," says Mario Sol Muntañola, a lawyer and expert in intellectual property. (Soufi 2023) Also, the article quotes a research done by Guillermo Marco and Julio Gonzalo, who are researchers in the field of Natural Language Processing. On how the AI writes poems, they state that "These models work like networks of artificial neurons, which are like our brain. What they do is learn to write through a cognitive simulation of how we read." Further in their experiment Guillermo Marco and Julio Gonzalo asked several participants to analyse some art pieces generated by AI and almost all of them said that the only one thing that the pieces lack is creativity; the ingenuity and artistry of the poet. This very well makes things clear as to how AI writes poems and in what ways it has limitations in the final piece of art..

Analysis of poems On Love

Prompt – "Write a short free verse poem on love."

Generated Poem -

In the vast expanse of life's unfolding canvas,
Love rests, unanchored by convention or form,
A force, boundless, untamed by seasons or reasons,
It moves like shadows over moonlit waters,
Intangible yet palpable, a paradox profound.

Echoing in the laughter of children,
In the touch of hands weathered by time,
In the silent language of shared memories,
It remains, undiminished, even as everything else fades.

Love, neither a beginning nor an end,
But a journey, a discovery,
A flame that neither wanes nor consumes,
But illuminates the very essence of our being.

Analysis-On asking to write a free verse poem on love, the generative AI ChatGPT returns

this poem. The poem talks about the potency of love and how it is not bound by "convention

or form”. The prompt asks ChatGPT to write a free verse poem, so it doesn’t use any rhyming scheme, but there is internal rhyme in the third line of the poem where “seasons or reasons” rhyme. This shows that the AI is following the conventions of the poem while generating a poetic text. The poem here uses superfluous language, devoid of any creativity which can differentiate this poem from any other poem written on love. However, the language model typically remembers to use literary devices like simile in the fourth line, where it

compares love to shadows which move “over moonlit waters”. In the second stanza, GPT tries to make some images of places where love can be found, on reading the lines the mind fails to picture some new images which up until now the reader is unaware of. Which points to the imaginative limitations of the AI, however the lines are not plagiarized. These sorts of images have a long literary history and thus fail to evoke any feelings of enchantment and mystic image of love.

On Happiness

Prompt – “write a Shakespearean sonnet on happiness”
Generated Poem -

In golden rays where happiness doth shine,
A gentle warmth that hearts with joy imbues,
’Tis but a fleeting dance, elusive, fine,
Yet in its embrace, all sorrow eschews.

The merry lark sings high with gleeful voice,
As laughter, love, and moments sweet entwine,
In life’s grand tapestry, a chosen choice,
To seek the light, and let one’s spirit pine.

Yet truest joy lies not in wealth or fame,
But simple moments, cherished, held so dear,
The whispered wind, the love that speaks our name,
The tender touch that wipes away a tear.

For happiness, a gem both rare and vast,
Is found in present joys and memories past.

On Remorse

Prompt – “Write a Shakespearean sonnet on remorse”

Generated Poem -

In shadows deep, where remorse doth reside,
A heavy burden on the soul doth lay,
For deeds of yore, wherein the heart hath lied,
In whispered echoes of a fateful day.

Oh, how the weight of actions done amiss,
Doth haunt the conscience with a mournful song,
The past’s regrets, a never-ending abyss,
Wherein the soul doth wrestle right from wrong.

Yet, in this sorrow, lessons may be found,
For remorse, a teacher harsh but wise,

It guides the way to higher, solid ground,
And clears the path where virtue often lies.

So, let us heed the call of remorse's voice,
And in its bitter depths, make wiser choice.

Analysis- When asked to write a Shakespearean sonnet on Happiness and Remorse, the following was the produce. It is exemplary of GPT as a language processing model on maintaining the rhyme scheme of Shakespearean sonnet and well utilising the information from its database about how “English sonnet, or else the Shakespearean sonnet ... falls into three quatrains and a concluding couplet: abab cdcd efef gg.” (Meyer Howard Abrams & Geoffrey Galt Harpham, 2013 p. 369). But worth noting is the fact that at the very onset it failed to keep up with one of the important feature i.e. Iambic Pentameter the rhythm of da-DUM, da-DUM, da-DUM..., although it has maintained the number of syllables . Another evident technicality of the sonnet that GPT did not apply is the rhyme pattern.

The rhyme pattern of the Petrarchan sonnet has on the whole favoured a statement of a problem, situation, or incident in the octave, with a resolution in the sestet. The English form sometimes uses a similar division of material but often presents instead a repetition-with-Generated Poem -

Beneath a sky so vast and blue,
My heart feels heavy, dreams askew.
Once by my side, you'd romp and play,
Now silence speaks where you once lay.

Your wagging tail, your joyful bark,
Now shadows cast in the quiet dark.
Each corner, each step, feels so bare,
Without your presence, without you there.

Oh, faithful friend, my heart does grieve,
For moments lost, for the reprieve.
But in the stars, I'll find your glow,
Remembering love, forever to show.

Analysis-This prompt asks GPT to write a poem expressing the feelings of a boy who has just lost his pet dog. So, GPT understands what to write about. The boy will obviously feel sad about losing his dog, so it goes on to write a sad poem. And for that it picks up sad words from

variation of a statement in each of the three quatrains; in either case, the final couplet in the English sonnet usually imposes an epigrammatic turn at the end. (Meyer Howard Abrams & Geoffrey Galt Harpham, 2013 p. 370)

In both the poems, the lack of creativity makes it crude to a level that no emotions of happiness or remorse is felt or conveyed. It is obvious that machines lag behind in even getting a grasp of what human emotions are and most importantly how subjective they are. As such of literary device, it managed to get one alliteration in the last line of the last quatrain of Happiness and none for Remorse. Metaphor is found when happiness is compared with a gem. Overall, what actually has been done is the collection of words and facts that when combined together in the verse form would resemble a poem on that specific emotion.

On Sadness- Prompt - “write a short lyrical poem with any meter of your choice expressing feelings of a boy who has just lost his beloved pet dog.”

its vocabulary, which means we can say almost all the words in the English language. GPT tries to indicate the sadness of the boy by writing lines like “heart feels heavy” and “silence speaks”, which is an excellent example of oxymoron. Since, GPT knows it has to write a

sad poem it includes the words like shadow and dark, and it does the same in the poems written on the emotions of remorse and anger. This is the main flaw in the language model, that it makes poetry writing a rule of thumb and applies it everywhere it sees fit. While reading the poem and keeping in mind, the rule that many creative writing experts and writers suggest to new writers is that don't write the words, show it. Meaning that if you want to write about some dark and terrifying room, do not just write how horrific the room looks. Show it to the reader through the words, and let the reader themselves feel the horror of the dark room. In the poem about sadness of a boy, GPT Generated Poem -

In yonder field, beneath the somber skies,
Where dreams were spun and hopes did rise,
We strove with might, with fervent cries,
Yet Fate, she smirked with cold, stern eyes.

The ball, like Fortune, slipped away,
Each missed chance, a dark display,
Oh, cruel turf! Where shadows lay,
You've turned our golden hopes to gray.

That fleeting goal, so near, yet far,
Like a wayward, unreachable star,
Anguish! Bitter as the deepest scar,
For we've tasted defeat, a bitter tar.

Yet in this fire of angered throes,
A fiercer spirit in us grows,
For though today's game to wind it goes,
Tomorrow, to challenge our foes.

Analysis-Since the prompt has the word Keatsian, GPT goes ahead and uses rhymes in every like aaaa bbbb cccc dddd, which Keats never did in his most known poems, he either used aabb ccdd or abab cdcd. The AI however seems to have learned that to use the dark words like shadows, gray, dark, cruel, scar, and cold in the negative sense and relating to defeat and anguish. The language model also does not fail to change the mood of the poem in the last to inspire to win the next game, and thus is somewhat motivating the reader in the course. In this poem as well there is a use of simile comparing the ball with fortune that slipped away leading to the defeat in a football game. Personification of fate, which smirked on the defeated team with cold and stern eyes. Though the poem very likely expresses the feeling of anger through the first three stanzas

simply writers in the final stanza "my heart does grieve", in spite of inventing some new way of expressing that the boy's heart grieves and let the reader themselves feel the pain, it takes the shortcut and writes the line in a simple word. This is where it lacks, in invention, because ChatGPT has learned everything from the Internet and does not have any intellect of its own. It does not possess its own intellect, rather is a language model which implies searching and sorting method of algorithm intelligently.

On Anger- Prompt – "Write a Keatsian type short lyrical poem which expresses anger of losing a football game."

and turns inspiring in the final stanza, it still lacks creativity. The poem looks very objective and that may not be the case if a research would be done on higher scale with huge inputs of poems written with varying prompts. However, at the generic prompt of writing just a poem on anger, GPT fails to convey the emotions in a new way which is the essence of writing and reading poems. Otherwise, there may not have been possible to write any new love poem at all because there may be poems written in all the ways possible. The human creativity and imagination finds new ways to express themselves which differs from all the previous written art pieces.

Conclusion-Though GPT can beat humans at the speed of producing a poem, can it beat it on the scale of creativity? The question is addressed in

the research done in this paper. The poems written by ChatGPT were analysed and found that meanwhile ChatGPT miraculously follows the conventions and art forms of any poem, but what it fails to follow is the intricacies inculcated in the poems written by humans. Throughout the poems written on various emotions, ChatGPT superficially prints lines which look like an amalgam of lines taken from poems written in various ages. GPT severely lacks imagination and creativity. It uses the words from contexts of emotions and writes it in the same way that human beings have written since ages.

The literary devices used by the ChatGPT also feel like they are used up, they do not have any newness in them, they feel like a neoclassical age poem with rigid language and set patterns. Often when humans write something, they like to experiment a bit to produce the matter with some newness and twist to cater to the audience. It is the utmost priority to not make the work dull and just another generic piece of literature. ChatGPT does not consider this prospect and just produces generic poems throughout genres and emotions. The question of emotion is also not tackled by ChatGPT, in the name of emotions it just uses the same old words in the same way devoid of any new ways of writing. By looking at the poem, it tries to convince the reader that it is a sad poem by using clichéd words like shadows, dark, cold, shiver, grieve and mourn. These sorts of poems remain unnoticed by the readers and considered as an amateur writing.

What limits ChatGPT in writing poems creatively, is the technology on which it has been built. GPT uses a searching and sorting algorithm to generate text from its database, which is

updated until 2021. So what GPT has, is a huge chunk of texts: novels, poems, essays, books, articles etc which it goes through and prepares a text. In this process, there is no real intelligence involved as such. Which again comes back to the question of which has been asked time and again, is ChatGPT a real AI? The question is not tough, ChatGPT is a language model, and it has limited knowledge, and it lacks creativity.

The results of a research may vary when using different prompts to generate poems, but what remains the same throughout all the poems generated is the superficiality of language and almost no creativity in the poems composed. The LLMs may succeed in generating generic poems and pieces of art, but we're a long way from an AI which creatively generates text and pieces of art with its own perception.

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